

Short Communication

Can the Bass innovation diffusion model describe adsorption breakthrough curves of pharmaceutical contaminants?

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HIGHLIGHTS

- The Bass model is widely used in business innovation and marketing research.
- It can function as a breakthrough curve model.
- It outperforms the Bohart–Adams model.
- Modified Bass model can describe highly asymmetric breakthrough curves.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

1. Introduction

Fixed bed adsorption is a widely used separation process in the chemical industry for the processing of liquids and gases. The performance of fixed bed adsorption systems is often evaluated by analyzing the breakthrough curves, which represent the variation of the solute concentration in the effluent stream as a function of time or bed volume. The development of accurate and reliable models for representing breakthrough curves is crucial for the design and optimization of fixed bed adsorbers and for the evaluation of their economic feasibility. In this context, mathematical models that describe the transport of solutes in the fixed bed and their interaction with the adsorbent material have been developed and extensively documented in the chemical engineering literature [1]. These models primarily rely on mass transfer mechanisms in the liquid and solid phases, which are expressed as partial differential equations and typically solved numerically.

Fixed bed adsorption is also a widely used technology for the treatment of contaminated liquid and gas streams. While mass transfer-based models can be used to analyze these processes [2], simple models expressed as algebraic equations dominate the modeling scene. These simple models have several advantages for describing contaminant breakthrough behavior, including their ease of application and accessibility to users without a chemical engineering background. They are also computationally efficient, allowing for quick analysis of large datasets through spreadsheet calculations. Among the simple models, the Bohart–Adams and Thomas models are widely employed, with the former serving as the basis for the bed depth-service time (BDST) design methodology used for sizing activated carbon columns [3].

The Bohart–Adams and Thomas models suffer from a notable drawback: they are unable to accurately represent the complete shape of experimental breakthrough curves, which often exhibit asymmetry [3,4]. As a result, a poor fit can lead to substantially inaccurate estimations of

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both breakthrough and exhaustion times. This limitation stems from the models' mathematical structure, which resembles the logistic equation, a function well-known for predicting symmetric sigmoid or S-shaped curves. Since adsorption breakthrough curves can be mathematically viewed as sigmoid patterns, researchers have explored the use of simple analytical functions developed in other fields as models for breakthrough curves. For instance, probability distributions like the normal [5,6] and Gompertz [7] functions have been applied to breakthrough curves of aqueous contaminants.

Our research aims to explore the suitability of the Bass model for innovation diffusion, a widely used model in the field of business innovation, as a breakthrough curve model. The Bass model offers a simple analytical expression that is commonly used to estimate the potential sales and adoption of new products or services in a market. Introduced by Frank Bass (1926–2006) [8,9] in 1969, it has found extensive applications in marketing and business research. In a recent study by Bingel and Walton [10], the Bass model was used to effectively fit experimental isotherms for gas adsorption, including S-shaped isotherms.

The primary objective of this study is to evaluate and compare the efficacy of the Bass model, a new version of it, and the Bohart-Adams model in accurately representing breakthrough data related to pharmaceutical adsorption in fixed bed columns. The presence of pharmaceutical contaminants in wastewater has raised significant concerns due to their potential long-term effects. Some pharmaceuticals have demonstrated persistence and bioaccumulation in the environment, leading to increased efforts in monitoring and minimizing their presence in wastewater as well as developing innovative technologies for their removal.

2. Breakthrough curve models

In the realm of quantitative marketing, innovation diffusion models are extensively used to predict the rate at which new products and services will be adopted. These models also aid in developing marketing strategies to encourage adoption and expedite the rate of growth. The adoption rate typically follows an S-shaped curve, initially starting slow, then accelerating as more individuals adopt the product, and eventually reaching a plateau as the market becomes saturated. Interestingly, there is a resemblance between the diffusion phenomenon and the increase in concentration at the exit of a fixed bed adsorber. Both phenomena exhibit sigmoid curves over time. Moreover, the ascent of the effluent concentration, constrained by an upper limit (the feed concentration), bears resemblance to the diffusion phenomenon, which encounters a limit in the form of market saturation. Among the models for innovation diffusion, the Bass model [8,9] is widely recognized as the most prominent and extensively studied model in the literature on marketing science.

The Bass model is represented by a first-order differential equation [8], which describes the process of innovation diffusion using three parameters. These parameters include the maximum market potential and two coefficients, p and s , that correspond to two different groups of adopters. Coefficient p is associated with innovators who are the initial adopters, while coefficient s pertains to imitators who adopt the innovation at a later stage, often influenced by word-of-mouth dynamics. The analytical solution to the differential equation is denoted by Eq. (1), where F represents the fraction of final adopters who have adopted the innovation at time t , and $p (>0)$ and $s (>0)$ are the coefficients associated with innovation and imitation, respectively.

$$F = \frac{1 - \exp[-(p+s)t]}{1 + (s/p)\exp[-(p+s)t]} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Modeling sulfamethoxazole breakthrough data with the mechanistic model of Juella et al. [11] (a), Bohart-Adams model (b), Bass model (c), and new Bass model (d).

In order to construct a breakthrough curve model based on the Bass model, Eq. (1) can be modified by substituting F with the dimensionless column effluent concentration c/c_0 , where c is the effluent concentration at time t and c_0 denotes the feed concentration. Additionally, the parameters p and s in Eq. (1) can be replaced with a and b , as shown in Eq. (2), where a is equal to s/p and b represents $(p + s)$.

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \frac{1 - \exp(-bt)}{1 + a \exp(-bt)} \quad (2)$$

This study presents a new version of the Bass model for breakthrough curves by introducing a logarithmic transformation to the variable t , specifically $\ln(t)$. Since the logarithmic function can only operate on dimensionless numbers, it is necessary to make the variable t , which represents time, dimensionless [4,7]. To achieve this, the following steps are taken. Initially, we assume that t is measured in units of minutes. Next, we multiply t by T/T , where T is set to 1 min. Consequently, we obtain $T(t/T)$, where the bracketed term represents a dimensionless quantity. Finally, we take the logarithm of (t/T) , resulting in $T\ln(t/T)$. Eq. (2) can now be written as Eq. (3), wherein t is replaced with $T\ln(t/T)$. It is important to note that in Eq. (3), the parameters a and b from Eq. (2) are replaced with α and β , respectively, to denote the unique parameters of the new Bass model. Considering that T is numerically equal to unity, it can be omitted from Eq. (3), leading to Eq. (4).

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \frac{1 - \exp[-\beta T \ln(t/T)]}{1 + \alpha \exp[-\beta T \ln(t/T)]} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \frac{1 - \exp[-\beta \ln(t)]}{1 + \alpha \exp[-\beta \ln(t)]} \quad (4)$$

Notably, the new Bass model defined by Eq. (4) can be further simplified to the form presented in Eq. (5). As demonstrated in prior studies [4,7], the logarithmic transformation technique proved effective in enhancing the data fitting capability of the Bohart–Adams model and the Gompertz equation. This improved performance was attributed to the modifications made to the inflection point of the predicted sigmoid curve [4,7].

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \frac{1 - t^{-\beta}}{1 + \alpha t^{-\beta}} \quad (5)$$

The original Bass model (Eq. (2)) and the new version (Eq. (4)) will be compared with the Bohart–Adams model, as expressed in Eq. (6). The Bohart–Adams model incorporates the parameters m and n , which are defined in Eqs. (7) and (8), respectively. In these equations, k_{BA} represents the Bohart–Adams rate coefficient, N denotes the quantity of contaminant adsorbed per unit volume of the packed bed, L is the length of the packed bed, and u corresponds to the superficial velocity.

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(m - nt)} \quad (6)$$

$$m = \frac{k_{BA}NL}{u} \quad (7)$$

$$n = k_{BA}c_0 \quad (8)$$

3. Results and discussion

In this study, we applied the three breakthrough curve models mentioned earlier (Bass, new Bass, and Bohart–Adams) to two previously published datasets concerning pharmaceutical adsorption in fixed bed columns. One of these datasets, provided by Juela et al. [11], presents a breakthrough curve for the adsorption of sulfamethoxazole in a fixed bed column packed with sugarcane bagasse, as illustrated in Fig. 1. Sulfamethoxazole is an antibiotic medication commonly used for treating

Table 1

Experimental details for sulfamethoxazole [11] and acetaminophen [13] adsorption in fixed bed columns packed with sugarcane bagasse.

Parameter	Contaminant	
	Sulfamethoxazole	Acetaminophen
Adsorbent diameter (mm)	0.59	0.59
Column diameter (cm)	4.4	1.5
Column length (cm)	50	33
Flow rate (cm ³ min ⁻¹)	20	2.5
Superficial velocity (cm min ⁻¹)	1.3	1.4
Empty bed contact time (min)	38	23.3
Feed concentration (mg L ⁻¹)	5	57

bacterial infections. Pertinent experimental details for this breakthrough curve are tabulated in Table 1.

The fixed bed experiment was conducted with an empty bed contact time (EBCT) of 38 min. Pilot-scale activated carbon column studies aimed at removing micropollutants, including human pharmaceuticals, from municipal wastewater treatment plant effluent have shown that optimal performance requires a minimum EBCT of 20–30 min [12]. As depicted in panel a of Fig. 1, the breakthrough of sulfamethoxazole occurred after approximately 30 min of operation. The breakthrough curve exhibited an asymmetric pattern, gradually approaching saturation. The fixed bed experiment was terminated after around 170 min of operation, reaching a dimensionless effluent concentration of approximately 84%.

Juela et al. [11] used a mechanistic model to predict the breakthrough data depicted in panel a of Fig. 1. The model is based on the linear driving force (LDF) approximation, the axially dispersed plug flow assumption, and the Langmuir equation for the equilibrium isotherm. Eqs. (9)–(11) outline the mathematical representation of the model. In these equations, c is the contaminant concentration in the liquid phase, q is the concentration within the adsorbent particles, t is time, x is the column axial coordinate, v is the liquid phase interstitial velocity, ρ_p is the adsorbent density, ε is the bed voidage, D_L is the axial dispersion coefficient, k_{LDF} is the LDF rate coefficient, q^* is the solid phase concentration in equilibrium with c , b_L is the Langmuir equilibrium constant, and q_s is the maximum adsorption capacity.

$$v \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + \rho_p \frac{(1 - \varepsilon)}{\varepsilon} \frac{\partial q}{\partial t} = D_L \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial x^2} \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} = k_{LDF}(q^* - q) \quad (10)$$

$$q^* = \frac{q_s b_L c}{1 + b_L c} \quad (11)$$

The mechanistic model was solved numerically using parameters estimated from batch experiments and engineering correlations. While the predicted breakthrough curve, as depicted in panel a of Fig. 1, aligns well with the initial phase of the experimental data, it tends to overestimate the effluent concentration during the latter stages of breakthrough.

To fit the three breakthrough curve models (Bohart–Adams, Bass, and new Bass) to the sulfamethoxazole breakthrough curve, we used the nonlinear regression method of GraphPad Prism for Windows. As shown in panel b of Fig. 1, the Bohart–Adams model fit results in a relatively low R^2 score of 0.912, indicating poor alignment with most of the data points. This outcome is expected since the mathematical structure of the Bohart–Adams model is limited to describing symmetric breakthrough curves. Additionally, the Bohart–Adams model has the drawback of predicting a non-zero effluent concentration at $t = 0$.

As illustrated in panel c of Fig. 1, the Bass model fit exhibits only a slight improvement ($R^2 = 0.936$) compared to the Bohart–Adams model fit, with notable discrepancies observed between the Bass model fit and

Table 2

Parameter estimates and statistical metrics for the fits of the Bohart–Adams, Bass, and new Bass models to sulfamethoxazole breakthrough data [11].

Model	Equation	Parameter	Value	Statistical metric	Value
Bohart–Adams	(6)	m	2.65	R^2	0.912
		n (min^{-1})	0.033	RMSE	0.089
Bass	(2)	a	5.41	R^2	0.936
		b (min^{-1})	0.026	RMSE	0.076
New Bass	(4)	α	80161	R^2	0.971
		β (min^{-1})	2.62	RMSE	0.051

the experimental data during the initial phase of breakthrough. Conversely, panel d of Fig. 1 shows that the new Bass model fit results in a substantially higher R^2 score of 0.971, surpassing both the Bohart–Adams and Bass model fits. It is evident that the new Bass model effectively captures the complete profile of the experimental breakthrough curve. The parameter estimates and statistical metrics, including the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the root mean square error (RMSE), obtained from the three model fits are summarized in Table 2.

The performance of the three models was further evaluated using a set of breakthrough data reported by Vera et al. [13]. Panel a of Fig. 2 displays the chosen breakthrough curve for acetaminophen adsorption in a fixed bed column packed with sugarcane bagasse. Acetaminophen, commonly known as paracetamol, is a widely used medication for fever reduction and pain relief. Table 1 provides a summary of the relevant system properties and operating conditions.

The mechanistic model based on the LDF approximation, which was previously used in the sulfamethoxazole analysis, was combined with a computational fluid dynamics model to predict the acetaminophen breakthrough profile [13]. Panel a of Fig. 2 presents the predicted breakthrough curve, which accurately represents the initial phase of

Table 3

Parameter estimates and statistical metrics for the fits of the Bohart–Adams, Bass, and new Bass models to acetaminophen breakthrough data [13].

Model	Equation	Parameter	Value	Statistical metric	Value
Bohart–Adams	(6)	m	3.99	R^2	0.928
		n (min^{-1})	0.088	RMSE	0.100
Bass	(2)	a	31.62	R^2	0.932
		b (min^{-1})	0.077	RMSE	0.097
New Bass	(4)	α	849637	R^2	0.960
		β (min^{-1})	3.61	RMSE	0.074

breakthrough but exhibits discrepancies in the final phase. Likewise, the Bohart–Adams, Bass, and new Bass models successfully replicate the initial breakthrough phase but fail to accurately describe the final stage, as illustrated in panels b, c, and d of Fig. 2. It is evident that none of the models can precisely predict the entire profile of the asymmetric breakthrough data. Nevertheless, panel d of Fig. 2 highlights the superior performance of the new Bass model, achieving an R^2 value of 0.960. The resulting parameter estimates for the three model fits, along with the corresponding statistical metrics, are tabulated in Table 3.

The gradual approach toward saturation observed in the breakthrough curves of sulfamethoxazole and acetaminophen, known as tailing, can be attributed to several factors. One such factor is the progressive reduction in adsorption rate due to the steric hindrance caused by adsorbed molecules at high surface coverage, resulting in extended tailing. The mechanistic model, which assumes a constant LDF rate coefficient, is unable to fully explain the strong tailing observed in the two breakthrough curves. To accurately predict this pronounced tailing, the LDF rate coefficient should decrease as surface coverage increases. Eq. (12) provides an example of such a rate coefficient [14], where k_{LDFM} is the maximum LDF rate coefficient, μ is a hindrance coefficient

Fig. 2. Modeling acetaminophen breakthrough data with the mechanistic model of Vera et al. [13] (a), Bohart–Adams model (b), Bass model (c), and new Bass model (d).

($0 \leq \mu \leq 1$), and λ is a positive coefficient ($\lambda > 0$) that accounts for the nonlinear increase in the steric hindrance effect. Considering the inadequate performance of the mechanistic model, it should be regarded as a semi-empirical model, and its mechanistic validity should be subject to scrutiny.

$$k_{LDF} = k_{LDFM} \left\{ \mu + (1 - \mu) \left[1 - \frac{q}{q_s} \right]^\lambda \right\} \quad (12)$$

Although the new Bass model is effective in modeling breakthrough data with tailing, it is limited by its reliance on empirical parameters. To overcome this limitation, it is proposed that the two parameters in the new Bass model, α and β , can serve similar roles as the m and n parameters in the Bohart-Adams model. This leads to the definitions of α and β as presented in Eqs. (13) and (14), respectively, where k_B represents the Bass rate coefficient and N_B denotes the adsorption capacity parameter. Given that N_B holds physical significance, it can be estimated from the area above the breakthrough curve. Consequently, the new Bass model only requires one fitting parameter, k_B , which can be adjusted to fit asymmetric breakthrough data. Through the use of Eqs. (13) and (14), the new Bass model emerges as a valuable tool for designing fixed bed adsorbers.

$$\alpha = \frac{k_B N_B L}{u} \quad (13)$$

$$\beta = k_B C_0 \quad (14)$$

4. Conclusions

Tailing is a common characteristic observed in the breakthrough curves of pharmaceutical contaminants. The mechanistic model based on the LDF approximation proved inadequate for accurately predicting breakthrough curves with pronounced tailing, as seen in the cases of sulfamethoxazole and acetaminophen. Similarly, the Bass model struggled to capture the asymmetric nature of these breakthrough curves and provided only marginal improvement over the Bohart-Adams model. In contrast, the new Bass model demonstrated superior performance. However, a limitation of the new Bass model lies in its reliance on empirical parameters that lack a direct connection to fixed bed and operating variables. Nonetheless, by equating the empirical parameters

of the new Bass model with those of the Bohart-Adams model, it becomes possible to use the new Bass model for the design of fixed bed adsorbers.

Declaration of competing interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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